

MINIMUM COST DESIGN OF LAMINATED CYLINDERS UNDER
INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL PRESSURE BY HYBRID CONSTRUCTION

S. Adali and B. Yakar
Department of Mechanical Engineering
University of Natal
King George V Avenue
Durban 4001
South Africa

ABSTRACT

Cylindrically orthotropic laminated cylinders are optimized with the objective of minimizing the material costs by hybridization. The designs are subject to a lower bound on the internal or external pressure and a total thickness constraint. The high strength material is employed in the inner or outer layer depending on the location of the pressure and its thickness constitutes the design objective. The critical pressure is determined by employing the maximum stress theory of failure. The minimum thickness of the high strength material is determined subject to a minimum pressure constraint. Numerical results are given for hybrid cylinders made of graphite and glass/epoxy materials. The percentage of material saving is determined as compared to an all graphite construction.

KEY WORDS: Hybrid cylinders; Optimization; Design methodology; Laminated cylinders; Failure criterion.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cost considerations play an important role in the selection of materials for a specific

structure. High cost of advanced composites such as graphite, boron and kevlar reinforced plastics is one of the factors inhibiting their wider use. Cost-effectiveness can be improved by hybridization whereby an inexpensive composite such as glass fiber is incorporated into the design of the structure.

In the present article, the minimum cost design of a laminated cylinder under internal or external pressure is obtained. The design problem involves the minimization of the thickness of the layer made of a high strength material with the structure satisfying the minimum pressure constraint. The inner and outer radii of the cylinder are specified as design inputs. The optimal design uses the minimum amount of the expensive material and as such constitutes the minimum cost solution. The maximum stress theory of failure is used in computing the critical pressure.

Optimization of hybrid laminates under buckling loads and free vibration has been studied in References (1-4). Optimal designs of non-hybrid pressure vessels have been given in (5-8). Laminated cylinders with a hybrid construction have been optimized under internal pressure in (9) and (10).

Numerical results are given for hybrid cylinders made of graphite and glass/epoxy materials. Efficiency of an optimal design is defined as the percentage material saving as compared to a cylinder made of graphite/epoxy only. It is observed that material savings of more than 30% can be achieved depending on the total thickness and the minimum pressure constraint. The minimum thickness of the graphite layer is found to be decreasing once the outer radius exceeds a certain value.

2. BASIC EQUATIONS

The laminated cylinder consists of two layers of different materials. The layers have cylindrical orthotropy with one of the material axes parallel to the longitudinal axis. The cylinder may be subjected to internal or external pressure denoted by p and q . Due to axisymmetrical loading and cylindrical orthotropy, the problem can be treated as a generalized plane strain problem.

The internal and external radii of the cylinder are denoted by a and b , respectively. The radius of the interface between the high and low strength material is given by a_1 where $a \leq a_1 \leq b$. The stress analysis for this problem is given in (11). Denoting the radial and circumferential coordinates by r and θ and, the internal and external layers

by subscripts 1 and 2, the stresses are given by

$$\sigma_{rm}(r) = q_{m-1} c_m^{k_m+1} R_{1m}^-(r)/C_m + q_m R_{2m}^-(r)/C_m \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{\theta m}(r) = q_{m-1} c_m^{k_m+1} k_m R_{1m}^+(r)/C_m - q_m k_m R_{2m}^+(r)/C_m \quad (2)$$

where $m=1$ or 2 is the layer number and

$$c_m = a_{m-1}/a_m, \quad a_0 = a, \quad a_2 = b, \quad k_m = (E_{\theta m}/E_{rm}) \quad (3)$$

$$R_{1m}^{\pm}(r) = (r/a_m)^{k_m-1} \pm (a_m/r)^{k_m+1} \quad (4)$$

$$R_{2m}^{\pm}(r) = \pm (r/a_m)^{k_m-1} + c_m^{k_m} (a_m/r)^{k_m+1} \quad (5)$$

$$C_m = 1 - c_m^{2k_m} \quad (6)$$

$$q_0 = p, \quad q_2 = q, \quad q_1 = -(p a \alpha_1 + q b \alpha_2)/a_1 \beta \quad (7)$$

$$\alpha_m = 2 k_m c_m^{k_m} / E_{\theta m} C_m \quad (8)$$

$$\beta = R_{31}/E_{\theta 1} - R_{32}/E_{\theta 2} \quad (9)$$

$$R_{3m} = \nu_{\theta m} + (-1)^m k_m (1 + c_m^{2k_m})/C_m \quad (10)$$

The elastic constants of the materials are denoted by E_{rm} , $E_{\theta m}$ and $\nu_{\theta m}$.

3. MINIMUM COST PROBLEM

The objective of the design optimization is to minimize the material cost of the hybrid construction by using the minimum amount of the high strength material subject to a lower bound on the pressure and for a given total thickness of the cylinder. The design procedure leads to hybrid laminates which uses the least amount of the expensive fiber

reinforcement. Let the thickness of the high strength material be denoted by t_{hs} and the critical internal or external pressure by P . The design problem can be stated as follows:

Minimum Cost Design

Determine the smallest thickness t_{hs} for a cylinder subject to a lower bound on the critical pressure and with given internal and external radii a and b , i.e., determine

$$t_{opt} = \min t_{hs}(P_{min}) \quad (11)$$

subject to

$$P \geq P_{min}, \quad 0 \leq t_{hs} \leq b-a \quad (12)$$

where P_{min} denotes the minimum specified pressure.

The lower bound P_{min} needs to satisfy certain conditions for the cost problem to be well defined. The largest value that P_{min} can take should be less than the maximum value of the critical pressure P_{hs} of a cylinder made of the high strength material. The smallest value of P_{min} should be larger than the critical pressure P_{ls} of a cylinder made of the low strength material. Thus, a hybrid cylinder with $0 < t_{hs} < b-a$ becomes the solution of the minimum cost problem only if

$$P_{ls} < P_{min} < P_{hs} \quad (13)$$

If P_{min} is less than the lower bound, then a non-hybrid (low-strength) cylinder provides the solution. If P_{min} is larger than P_{hs} , then a solution does not exist with given radii.

4. METHOD OF SOLUTION

The maximum pressure, referred to as the critical pressure, is computed by adopting

the theory of maximum stress as the failure criterion. Let $\bar{\sigma}_{\theta m}$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{r m}$ denote the stresses in the m-th layer corresponding to a unit pressure $P=1$. The stresses for any pressure P are given by

$$\sigma_{\theta m} = \bar{\sigma}_{\theta m} P, \quad \sigma_{r m} = \bar{\sigma}_{r m} P \quad (14)$$

The maximum stress criteria are expressed as

$$X_{cm} \leq \sigma_{\theta m} \leq X_{tm}, \quad Y_{cm} \leq \sigma_{r m} \leq Y_{tm} \quad (15)$$

where X_{tm} , X_{cm} , Y_{tm} and Y_{cm} are the tensile and compressive strengths of the composite material in the fiber and transverse directions. Substituting equations (14) into equations (15), the failure pressures P_{im} for the m-th layer are obtained as

$$P_{1m} = X_{tm} / \bar{\sigma}_{\theta m} \text{ for } \bar{\sigma}_{\theta m} > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad P_{1m} = X_{cm} / \bar{\sigma}_{\theta m} \text{ for } \bar{\sigma}_{\theta m} < 0 \quad (16)$$

$$P_{2m} = Y_{tm} / \bar{\sigma}_{r m} \text{ for } \bar{\sigma}_{r m} > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad P_{2m} = Y_{cm} / \bar{\sigma}_{r m} \text{ for } \bar{\sigma}_{r m} < 0 \quad (17)$$

The critical failure pressure P_{cr} is given by

$$P_{cr} = \min_{i,m} \min_r P_{im}(r) \quad (18)$$

where $i, m=1,2$ and $a \leq r \leq b$.

5. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The optimal designs are presented for a hybrid cylinder made of graphite/epoxy (T300/5208) and glass/epoxy (Scotchply 1002) materials. The elastic constants and strength values for graphite/epoxy are $E_L=181$ Gpa, $E_T=10.3$ GPa, $G_{LT}=7.17$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.28$, $X_t=-X_c=1500$ MPa, $Y_t=40$ MPa, $Y_c=-246$ MPa. The corresponding constants for glass/epoxy are $E_L=38.6$ Gpa, $E_T=8.27$ GPa, $G_{LT}=4.14$ GPa, $\nu_{12}=0.26$, $X_t=1062$ MPa, $X_c=-610$ MPa, $Y_t=31$ MPa, $Y_c=-118$ MPa.

The results are given separately for cylinders under internal and external pressure. The largest value of b/a is taken as 1.3 which has been found to be the limit of accuracy of the thin cylinder theory implemented in this study (see (10)).

Hybrid Cylinders under Internal Pressure

In this case, the high strength material, i.e., graphite/epoxy, is employed in the inner layer so that the hybrid cylinder consists of a graphite fiber inner layer and a glass fiber outer layer.

For a well defined problem, the lower bound p_{\min} on the internal pressure should satisfy the inequality $p_{gl} \leq p_{\min} \leq p_{gr}$ where p_{gl} and p_{gr} denote the critical pressures of all glass and all graphite cylinders with the inner and outer radii taken as a and b . In the numerical results p_{\min} is taken as $p_{\min} = p_{gl} + w (p_{gr} - p_{gl})$ where $0 \leq w \leq 1$. Efficiency is defined as

$$E_f = 100 (t_{gr} - t_{opt}) / t_{gr} \quad (18)$$

where t_{gr} denotes the thickness of an all graphite cylinder the critical pressure of which is equal to p_{\min} . E_f indicates the percentage saving of high strength material which is realized as a result of a hybrid construction instead of an all graphite construction. In the figures, t_{opt} values are normalized with respect to the inner radius a and the unit of p_{\min} is MPa.

Figure 1 shows the curves of t_{opt} , efficiency and p_{\min} plotted against the ratio b/a for $p_{\min} = 0.5 (p_{gl} + p_{gr})$. After an initial flat region, p_{\min} increases as b/a becomes larger. It is observed that t_{opt} decreases for $b/a > 1.23$. Thus, the thickness of the graphite layer can be reduced by increasing the outer radius.

Figure 2 shows the curves of t_{opt} and efficiency plotted against p_{\min} . It is observed that material savings of more than 30% can be achieved for smaller values of p_{\min} .

FIGURE 1. Optimal t , efficiency and minimum p vs b/a

FIGURE 2. Optimal t and efficiency vs minimum p for $b/a=1.2$

Hybrid Cylinders under External Pressure

In this case, the high strength material, i.e., graphite/epoxy, is employed in the outer layer so that the hybrid cylinder consists of a graphite fiber outer layer and a glass fiber inner layer.

The lower bound q_{\min} on the external pressure satisfies the inequality $q_{gl} \leq q_{\min} \leq q_{gr}$ where q_{gl} and q_{gr} denote the critical pressures of all glass and all graphite cylinders with the inner and outer radii a and b .

Figure 3 shows the curves of t_{opt} , efficiency and q_{\min} plotted against b/a for $q_{\min} = 0.5 (q_{gl} + q_{gr})$. It is found that the critical external pressure levels off for $b/a > 1.23$, but the thickness of the graphite layer also decreases for $b/a > 1.23$.

FIGURE 3. Optimal t , efficiency and minimum q vs b/a

6. CONCLUSIONS

The cost of the material used in the construction of a cylindrically orthotropic cylinder is minimized by means of hybridization. The hybrid structure has the high strength material in the inner or outer layers depending on the location of the pressure. The thickness of this layer is minimized subject to a lower bound on the pressure. The hybrid construction provides the optimal solution if the minimum pressure is higher than the critical pressure of a cylinder made of the low strength material and smaller than that of a cylinder made of the high strength material.

Numerical results are given for graphite/glass cylinders under internal or external pressure. The effects of the total cylinder thickness and the minimum pressure constraint are investigated on the cost and the efficiency. As the total thickness increases, the thickness of the graphite layer increases upto a certain point after which it decreases. Material savings of more than 30% can be achieved by hybrid construction depending on the input parameters.

The material costs make up a considerable part of the expenses for structures made of advanced composites. Improving the cost-effectiveness of these structures by hybridization provides an efficient way of reducing costs.

REFERENCES

1. M. Miki and K. Tonomura, *Proceedings of 4th Int. Conf. on Composite Structures*, Elsevier Applied Science, London, 1987, pp. 1.368-1.377.
2. S. Adali and K. J. Duffy, *Composite Structures*, **14**, 49-60 (1990).
3. K. J. Duffy and S. Adali, *Composite Structures*, **14**, 113-124 (1990).
4. K. J. Duffy and S. Adali, *J. Sound and Vibration*, **145**, (1991).
5. C. C. Chao, C. T. Sun and S. L. Koh, *J. of Composite Materials*, **9**, 55-66 (1975).
6. T. R. Tauchert, *J. of Composite Materials*, **15**, 390-402 (1981).
7. H. Fukunaga and M. Uemura, *Composite Structures*, **1**, 31-49 (1983).

8. H. Fukunaga and T-W. Chou, *J. of Composite Materials*, **22**, 1156-1169 (1988).
9. A. Yao, *Proceedings of 5th Int. Conf. on Composite Structures*, Elsevier Applied Science, London, 1989, pp. 637-645.
10. A. K. Roy and S.W. Tsai, *ASME J. of Pressure Vessel Technology*, **110**, 255-262, (1988).
11. S. L. Lekhnitskii, *Anisotropic Plates*, Gordon and Breach Science Publishers, New York, 1968.